

DEVELOPMENT OF TYPES OF FINANCIAL SERVICES

Yuldoshev Obbos Amonovich

Teacher at Turon University

Email: abbosyuldashev667@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14243387>

Abstract. In the article, increasing the quality and speed of banking services is considered an important priority in the development of the financial services sector, and it shows the advantages of using banking services based on digital technologies.

Keywords. financial services, banking, digital technology, digital banking, blockchain.

Introduction

Research conducted by international organizations has shown that the introduction of financial technologies can increase the profitability of financial institutions by 20%. For example, according to research conducted by Insider Monkey, the highest-profit sector in 2021, that is, during the pandemic, was various software products (applications and systems), with a return on capital of 32.07% during this period [5].

Literature Review

Due to the fact that financial services are mainly based on implementation through banks, several modern scientists are covering the issue of banking transformation in scientific articles. In particular, S.V. Krivoshapova noted that "billing, speed of payments and cash services are one of the important problems in credit organizations" [1]. T.A. Vasileva pointed out that banks are no longer the sole owners of unique information, and due to the development of financial instruments, transactions are concluded without bank intervention, and as an example, "complete contracts" offered by non-bank financial intermediaries are cited [2].

Analysis and Results

As a result of the implementation of new standards for financial services in Uzbekistan's banking structures, a number of positive changes can be observed. In particular, payments for purchased goods and services are made through bank plastic cards, and transactions are carried out through banks. This creates convenience for the population in providing financial services (Diagram 1).

Diagram 1

Payments Made via POS Terminals*

(billion UZS)

* Compiled by the author after studying the official data of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan. – <https://cbu.uz/ru>.

The data indicates that payments through POS terminals increased significantly between 2019 and 2023. For instance, payment volumes grew by 183 699.1 billion UZS during this period (254 719.1 – 71 020.0), reflecting a 358.6% increase or a 3.5-fold rise.

Additionally, in 2020, the Central Bank of Uzbekistan introduced a **QR-online** payment system, enabling buyers to make payments for goods and services without the need for bank cards or POS terminals. This system requires merchants to request a QR code from their bank, which buyers can scan using their mobile applications to complete payments instantly. Such innovations have undoubtedly improved the efficiency and convenience of transactions.

Despite these successes, certain challenges remain in improving financial services for the population. These include:

- Low digital literacy among the population;
- Ensuring data security;
- Improving internet speed, particularly in remote regions.

To address these issues, several measures must be implemented.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Despite notable successes, there are several challenges in enhancing financial services for the population. Addressing these issues requires the implementation of specific measures, including:

1. Improving Digital Literacy

- Enhance public knowledge through educational programs and demonstrations via television and online platforms.

2. Advancing Digital Banking Services

- Increase the variety of digital banking applications and enrich them with new features to create convenience for customers.

- Develop banking models that align with existing economic relationships.

3. Investing in Infrastructure

- Focus on improving internet speed, particularly in remote areas, to enhance the quality of remote banking services.

4. Strengthening Security Measures

- Ensure the confidentiality of customers' personal information and the security of money transfer transactions.

- Expand the use of biometric authentication, digital identification, blockchain, and other advanced technologies.

5. Developing Human Resources

- Provide continuous training for bank employees to increase their proficiency in using modern digital technologies.

6. Establishing Legal Norms

Accelerating the development of legal standards for the use of digital banking technologies and their promotion.

List of Literature:

1. Krivoshapova S.V, Latvin E.A. Actual problems and perspective development of the raschetno-kassovykh operational client's credit organization of the RF. // Electronic scientific and practical magazine "Sovremye nauchnye issledovaniya i innovatsii". // <https://web.snauka.ru/issues/2014/11/41074>.

2. Vasileva T.A. Concept bank. 3.0: Global trends and consequences // Open Journal Systems. [Electronic resource]. - URL: <http://fkd.org.ua/article/view/107714/105099>.

3. Azlarova A, & Rakhmatullaeva M. (2022). Transformation of the banking sector - neot'emlemaya chast processa stanovleniya tsifrovoy ekonomiki v Respublike Uzbekistan. Science and scientific potential: basis of sustainable innovation development society, 1(1), 34–37.

// <https://doi.org/10.47689/inlibrary-sspbsids-2022>

4. Erdonaev A. Teoreticheskie osnovy transformatsii kommercheskikh bankov. // "Rynok, dengi i kredit" ejemesyachnyy ekonomicheskii nauchno-prakticheskiy zurnal, 4/2023. S.-3-11.

5. Vnimanie k klientu - osnova raboty: v Sberbanke rasskazali o principakh klientotsentrichnosti - RIAMO (riamo.ru). // <https://riamo.ru/article/288179>.